

Assessment of Digital Literacy Skills for Supporting Off-Campus Teaching at Selected University Libraries in Kenya

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Abstract

University libraries in Kenya are deficiently prepared to launch and operationalize full-fledged off-campus information products and services; hence, the wavering support for off-campus learning and teaching. The purpose of this study was to assess the digital literacy skills of selected university libraries in supporting off-campus teaching. The study was anchored on the technological pedagogical content knowledge model. Data was obtained from Kenyatta, Nairobi and Kenya College of Accountancy universities. A descriptive survey research design was employed and the target population was 127 university library staff and 491 faculty members from business, education, information technology, and graduate studies departments. Census of all the library staff was done, while a sample size of 220 faculty members was obtained using a stratified sampling technique. A semi structured questionnaire was used to collect the data. Validity and reliability tests were conducted on the data instrument. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and thematic analysis. The findings indicated that digital literacy skills had a positive and significant relationship with off-campus teaching at selected university libraries in Kenya. The study concluded that digital literacy skills had a positive and significant relationship with off-campus teaching at selected university libraries in Kenya. The study recommended library management to strengthen digital literacy skills. In particular, the library management should focus on the following critical skills: literacy searching skills, citing and referencing skills, literature synthesizing skills, and scholarly writing skills. The study makes significant contribution to policy, theory and practice in the field of information science.

Keywords: *Digital Literacy Skills, Selected University Libraries, Off-Campus Teaching*

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1.0 Introduction

Off-campus teaching and learning offers students a way to pursue their studies without substantially affecting some aspects of their lives, such as work, family life, and community commitments (Henderson et al., 2017). Digital literacy is the ability to find, analyze, develop and communicate information using technology; and which includes cognitive and technological skills (Becker, 2018). In a digital world, a digitally literate person can perform tasks. Most university libraries in developed countries have been building robust digital collections to support off-campus learners (Murray, 2015).

In Finland, university libraries are stocked with relevant learning resources both in print and electronic forms; namely e-books, and e-journals; and have well-trained librarians and automated libraries (Wibrowski et al., 2016). In developing nations, there is growing evidence of massive progress in the last few years to improve digital libraries in support of off-campus teaching and learning in Africa (Ilahi et al., 2017; Rosenberg, 2006). Digital preparedness has been given much attention in countries such as Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, and Nigeria as evidenced by the existence of digital libraries (Oyeleye & Uche, 2015; Wangila, 2014).

The University of Nairobi is considered to be the largest public University in Kenya. It provides online teaching and learning programs across various disciplines. Kenyatta University (KU) is regarded as the second-largest public tertiary institution in Kenya. The renowned KU's Post-Modern

Library is regarded as the largest library within Kenya, East Africa; and is on the list of top ten university libraries within Africa. Its goal is to be a top-tier university library supporting the provision of information services and amenities to its learners and researchers (KU, 2016). KCA is one of the fast-growing private Universities in Kenya and has also adopted the use of off-campus teaching program.

“Successful technology incorporation for teaching and learning involves expertise and the ability to navigate the relationships between technology, pedagogy and content”

Problem Statement

Kenyan universities are required to develop supportive ICT enablers for off-campus teaching. However, it is notable that most university libraries are deficiently prepared to implement off-campus teaching programs. A glaring case in point is where most Sub-Saharan university libraries were caught unawares and unprepared during the COVID-19 outbreak, since most of them had neither framework nor modalities of switching to and supporting online teaching. The COVID-19 pandemic was characterized by disruptions of academic activities (Areba, 2020). The state of unpreparedness can be attributed to lack of necessary capacity to support on-line library services. This situation is mirrored

at universities such as Kenyatta University library where less digital awareness, insufficiency of ICT resources, lack of digital literacy skills, inadequate staff training, insufficient fiscal resources, and employee turnover had been noted (KLISC, 2016). The magnitudes of these impediments have not been validated at university libraries, and there exists few empirical studies that have explored the underlying circumstances to inform digital literacy policy changes.

Research Objective

To assess the digital literacy skills for supporting off-campus teaching at selected university libraries in Kenya.

Literature on Digital Literacy Skills and Off-Campus Teaching

The Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model propagated by Mishra and Koehler (2006) underpins this study. The model embodies the long-term goal of building a school for self-renewal and emphasizes the primary position at the school level to mediate change and reflect on school problems and internal conditions (Tondeur, 2007). The model highlights the importance of specific priorities and systemic plans at the school level to guide educational innovation. In this paper, TPACK model is appropriate because it stresses the value of digital preparedness in promoting teaching.

According to this model, successful technology incorporation for teaching and learning involves expertise and the ability to navigate the relationships between technology, pedagogy and content. The

focus of this paper was on digital literacy skills and its influence on off-campus teaching. In line with the TPACK model, digital literacy skills can be linked to effective e-teaching. The TPACK model created a suitable foundation for establishing the relationship between digital literacy skills and off-campus teaching.

Argentina et al. (2014) analyzed the influence of digital skills on educational success in Italy and found no significant link between interactive skills and academic performance. Yang (2018) discussed the relationship between students' digital literacy and their attitudes towards the use of information and communication technology in Pakistan. The results showed that digital literacy, use of tablets and smartphones, previous computer training, and frequency of computer use had a significant influence on students' attitudes towards using ICT. The study introduced the concept of students' attitudes and how it is affected by their digital literacy.

Ukwoma et al. (2016) examined the extent to which Nigerian university students apply digital skills in their academic work. The study found that some students have digital skills and often use those skills for digital literacy. Most of the respondents stated that digital literacy had a significant impact on their academic success. The main barriers to acquiring digital skills were power outages, poor internet bandwidth, ICT services, lack of growth in the digital skills curriculum, and expectations. The study highlights major hindrances to acquiring digital skills. However, it does not specify the various digital skills that students possess, thus it is crucial to consider various digital literacy skills.

Omosekejimi et al. (2018) examined ICT and digital skills in Nigerian higher education institutions as tools for effective teaching. The total population consisted of teachers at four educational colleges in southwest Nigeria. Results indicated that ICT and digital skills were effective tools for effective teaching. Teachers mostly used computers, printers, copiers, projectors, virtual whiteboards / electronic mailboxes, and internet facilities. The study also showed that a large proportion of teachers in Nigerian educational colleges were prohibited from using PowerPoint, Excel, spreadsheets, and real computers to solve academic problems. According to the study, digital skills are essential for effective teaching. However, the study failed to cite examples of digital skills that are key to effective teaching.

2.0 Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Kenyatta, Nairobi and Kenya College of Accountancy universities. A descriptive survey research design was employed. The target population was 127 university library staff and 491 faculty members from business, education, information technology, and graduate studies departments. A census of all the library staff was done. Yamane's (1967) formula was adopted in the computation of the sample size from the faculty members. A sample size of 220 faculty members was

selected using stratified sampling technique. The faculty members were classified into four strata; namely, business, education, information technology, and graduate studies. Quantitative and qualitative data were collected using semi structured questionnaires.

Content, construct, face, and criterion validity of the instrument were investigated in this study. Reliability of the instrument was checked using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, and percentages), and correlation analysis, while qualitative data was analyzed thematically. Correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variable.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Findings on Digital Literacy Skills

The study established the digital literacy skills at selected University libraries for supporting off-campus teaching. The respondents were asked to rate their digital literacy skills. The items presented to respondents were about search skills, communication, safety, evaluation, and creativity. The scale used was as follows: very Low (1), Low (2), moderately low (3), High (4), very High (5). Table 1 shows the outcome.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics on Digital literacy skills

Statements on Digital literacy skills (N=225)	1	2	3	4	5	M	Std. Dev
Literacy searching skills	0	0	14(6.2%)	93(41.3%)	118(52.4%)	4.5	0.6
Digital communication skills	0	7(3.1%)	37(16.4%)	117(52%)	64(28.4%)	4.1	0.8
Digital safety skills	0	15(6.7%)	52(23.1%)	77(34.2%)	81(36%)	4.0	0.9
Literature evaluation skills	0	31(13.8%)	15(6.7%)	85(37.8%)	94(41.8%)	4.1	1.0
Literature synthesizing skills for handling information content from different sources	0	0	38(16.9%)	84(37.3%)	103(45.8%)	4.3	0.7
Scholarly writing skills	0	0	45(20%)	62(27.6%)	118(52.4%)	4.3	0.8
Citing and referencing skills	0	0	32(14.2%)	53(23.6%)	140(62.2%)	4.5	0.7
Aggregate score						4.2	0.8

Table 1 shows that majority of respondents ranked their digital literacy skills as excellent. An aggregate mean of 4.2 and a standard deviation of 0.8 backed this up. Notably, most of the respondents rated very high their literacy searching skills (118, 52.4%), m=4.5), and citing and referencing skills (140, 62.2%), m=4.5). This implies that the respondents had good literacy searching, citing, and referencing skills, which are key digital literacy skills.

The findings concurred with Ukwoma et al. (2016) assertion that digital literacy skills are key in enhancing digital preparedness. Similarly, the current study brings out literacy searching, citing, and referencing skills as vital digital literacy skills. Further, the respondents rated high their literature

synthesizing skills in handling information content from different sources (103, 45.8%), m=4.3), and scholarly writing skills (118, 52.4%), m=4.3). This implied that most of the respondents had adequate digital literacy skills. It was expected that they would utilize these skills to support off-campus teaching. According to Herguner (2017), aspects of digital literacy include being able to access the internet; discovering, handling, and editing digital content; entering communications, and otherwise communicating with an online network of information and communications.

While highlighting other ways that one can improve digital literacy skills for supporting off-campus teaching in their

institutions, the respondents highlighted the following themes:

- Involvement of library and faculty staff in the formulation of information literacy syllabus and teaching
- Investing time in research and informational sessions for literacy skills
- Taking an online course to enhance the skills

These responses bring out the importance of digital literacy skills in supporting off-campus teaching. One main aspect is the involvement of library and faculty staff in formulating information literacy, syllabus and teaching. This will ensure that the staff understands the digital literacy skills needed to support off-campus training. There is also a need to invest time in research and informational sessions for literacy skills. This will ensure that faculty members and library staff have adequate

digital literacy skills to support e-learning. Further, the respondents noted the importance of taking an online course to enhance their skills. This will strengthen their digital literacy skills. These findings mirror Yang (2018) argument that digital literacy skills are fundamental in enhancing digital education. The results also support Andema's (2014) assertion that digital literacy is important in promoting online learning and teaching.

Findings on Off-Campus Teaching

The respondents rated statements on the dependent variable, which was off-Campus teaching. This variable was measured using various items that covered issues on program flexibility, e-teaching and learning materials, course quality, stakeholder cooperation, networking and enrollment. The scale used was as follows: very small extent (1), to a small extent (2), to a moderate extent (3), to large extent (4), to a very large extent (5). The descriptive results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics on Off-Campus Teaching

Statements on Off-Campus Teaching (N=225)	1	2	3	4	5	M	Std. Dev
The off-campus library services offer flexibility to lecturers	0	0	53(23.6%)	76(33.8%)	96(42.7%)	4.2	0.8
There are adequate e-teaching materials in library to facilitate off-campus teaching	23(10.2%)	8(3.6%)	44(19.6%)	86(38.2%)	64(28.4%)	3.7	1.2
Courses offered through off-campus teaching program have adequate e-resources provided by library	0	30(13.3%)	54(24%)	86(38.2%)	55(24.4%)	3.7	1.0
There is stakeholder cooperation including library administration in management of the off-campus teaching program	8(3.6%)	16(7.1%)	84(37.3%)	70(31.1%)	47(20%)	3.6	1.0
The off-campus teaching program provides faculty with opportunity for networking with library	0	16(7.1%)	29(12.9%)	94(41.8%)	86(38.2%)	4.1	0.9

The off-campus teaching has increased faculty-librarian liaison and cooperation	0	8(3.6%)	53(23.6%)	99(44%)	65(28.9%)	4.0	0.8
The availability of ICT resources has made off-campus teaching to flourish	8(3.6%)	16(7.1%)	61(27.1%)	83(36.9%)	66(29.3%)	3.9	1.0
Digital literacy skills is critical in supporting off-campus teaching	0	16(7.1%)	21(9.3%)	87(38.7%)	110(48.9%)	4.3	0.8
Staff training is a necessity in supporting off-campus teaching	0	16(7.1%)	14(6.2%)	40(17.8%)	164(72.9%)	4.6	0.7
The library has carried out activities to increase awareness of digital teaching enablers	0	0	90(40%)	71(31.6%)	64(28.4%)	3.9	0.8
Aggregate score						4.0	0.9

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents agreed to a great extent with the majority of the assertions about off-campus instructions. An aggregate mean of 4.0 and a standard deviation of 0.9 backed this up. The participants agreed to a very large extent that staff training is a necessity in supporting off-campus teaching (164, 72.9%), $m=4.6$). This implies that the respondents considered staff training as essential in supporting off-campus training. The findings concurred with the argument that training university staff is essential in enhancing new technological advancements by Abouelenein (2016).

Further, the respondents agreed to a large extent with the following statements: the off-campus library services offer flexibility to lecturers (96, 42.7%), $m=4.2$); the off-campus teaching program provides faculty with opportunity for networking with the library (86, 38.2%), $m=4.1$); the off-campus teaching has increased faculty-librarian liaison and cooperation (65, 28.9%), $m=4.0$); and digital literacy skills are critical in supporting off-campus teaching (110, 48.9%), $m=4.3$). According to this data, the majority of respondents recognized the value of digital preparation in strengthening off-campus teaching. The

findings corroborated with Mtega and Benard (2014) assertion that e-learning programs enhance online teaching and learning. This suggested that digital preparedness was essential in improving off-campus teaching.

When asked to suggest other ways to improve the library's support for off-Campus teaching in their institution, the respondents gave several responses which were thematically analyzed and categorized into three themes; namely, capacity building of staff; strong digital library services; and awareness of off-campus resources.

The respondents emphasized the importance of strengthening the capacity of the staff. This can be achieved through training and the provision of ICT resources. Damilola (2013) pointed out to a lack of awareness and ICT resources as obstacles to effective e-learning. As such, strengthening the capacity of the staff is essential for supporting off-campus teaching. The respondents also noted the need to have strong digital library policies that support off-campus teaching. In particular, stakeholders should be included in the development of the policies. The findings supported Alfrih's (2017)

argument on the importance of engaging stakeholders. Further, the respondents cited the need to create more awareness on off-campus resources. This would ensure that more staff and students are aware of off-campus resources. These findings mirrored Lwoga et al. (2015) argument that the creation of ICT awareness among teachers was essential in enhancing teaching.

The respondents were further asked to state the challenges libraries face in supporting off-Campus teaching. The following were identified as the key challenges.

- Low internet coverage
- Lack of proper policies
- Lack of adequate training

From the responses, it is evident that libraries face several challenges that may hinder the success of off-Campus teaching. The respondents cited low internet coverage as one of the main challenges facing off-campus teaching. According to Yildiz-Durak (2019), the internet is one of the most essential factors in encouraging students to use technology in the classroom. This means that lack of good internet connectivity would hinder effective off-Campus teaching.

The respondents also noted a lack of adequate training as a problem facing libraries in supporting off-Campus teaching. Training is key in ensuring that

the staff acquires necessary digital skills that will boost online teaching. Abouelenein (2016) emphasized the essence of training university staff in line with new technological advancements. This denotes that lack of adequate training could hinder library staff and faculty members in supporting off-Campus teaching.

Lack of proper policies was also cited as a major challenge. In particular, there lacks the inclusion of stakeholders in the digital preparedness process. Alfrih (2017) supported the importance of engaging stakeholders in the digital preparedness process to ensure that everyone is on board. However, the full involvement of stakeholders in the digital preparedness process appears to be missing in the universities, and this could hinder off-campus teaching.

Correlation between Digital Literacy Skills and Off-Campus Teaching

The correlation results were used to answer the question: what digital literacy skills do staff at selected university libraries have for supporting off-campus teaching?

Pearson correlation coefficient was used to compute the correlation between the independent variable (digital literacy skills) and the dependent variable (off-campus teaching). Results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Correlation Results; digital literacy skills and off-campus teaching

	Off-campus teaching	Digital literacy skills
Off-campus teaching	1	
Digital literacy skills	.331**	1
	.000	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results in Table 3 showed that digital literacy skills ($r = .331^{**}$, $P = .000$), had a weak positive and significant association with off-campus teaching at selected university libraries. This suggests that improvement in digital literacy skills is statistically and significantly correlated with off-campus teaching. Argentina et al. (2014) discovered a considerable positive association between digital opportunity and academic success. Similarly, the findings supported Yang (2018) revelation that digital literacy, use of tablets and smartphones, previous computer training, and frequency of computer use had a significant influence on students' attitudes towards using ICT.

5.0 Conclusion

The paper concluded that digital literacy skills had a positive and significant

relationship with off-campus teaching at selected university libraries in Kenya. This implies that digital literacy skills contribute significantly to off-campus teaching. The key aspects of focus in digital literacy skills were literacy searching skills, citing and referencing skills, literature synthesizing skills, and scholarly writing skills.

6.0 Recommendations

The study recommended library management to strengthen digital literacy skills. In particular, the library management should focus on the following critical skills: literacy searching skills, citing and referencing skills, literature synthesizing skills, and scholarly writing skills. Improving these aspects will boost the digital literacy skills of the faculty members, thus enhancing off-campus teaching.

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